
A Cross-Sectional Study Of Defense Mechanisms In Patients Of Depressive Disorders With Co-Morbid Substance Use Disorder

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Abstract:

Background: Coping with stress, substance use, recovery or interventions for mental health disorders have shown to be related with type and pattern of defence mechanism used. Hence, the current study aims to determine the relation between defence mechanisms and substance use in patients with Depressive disorders. **Materials and methods:** A cross sectional analytical study was conducted on 84 patients in the department of Psychiatry of a tertiary care teaching hospital in Chennai. Those fulfilled the eligibility criteria of age 18-59 years and having depression were categorised into those using substance and those who do not use. Hamilton Depression Scale was used to assess the severity of depression and a shortened version of Defence Style Questionnaire (DSQ) was used to assess the defence mechanism. Ethical clearance was obtained from institutional ethical committee. **Results:** The study was conducted on a sample of 84 people with depression. The median (IQR) age of onset of the disease was 37 (32-44.7) years. The overall median depression score was 15 (11-18). The level of depression was significantly higher among substance users than non-users. Projection (7.0) followed by rationalisation (6.7) and regression (6.4) were the most common defence mechanisms among substance users with depression. Majority of males were using substance. The proportion of substance use was higher among those who had studied only up to school or lower, among labourers and people in lower socio-economic class than their counterparts. **Conclusion:** The study concludes that different pattern of defense mechanisms were used in patients with depression with and without substance use, Projection followed by Rationalisation were the most common defence mechanism among substance users with depression, whereas, Denial followed by Reaction formation and Idealization were the common defense mechanisms among depression without substance use group which would be useful in better understanding of patients and application in psychotherapy.

Keywords: Defense mechanisms, Depression, Substance use disorders, India

Introduction

Defence mechanisms are an important indicator of personality functioning and predictor of severity in mental health disorders like depression.¹ Defence mechanisms are wide range of responses to stressors occurring in many physiological or pathological conditions.¹ Anna Freud has defined defence mechanisms as "unconscious resources used by the ego" to reduce internal stress and conflict between the superego and id.² These mechanisms help to maintain psychological homeostasis by forming a transition phase during any sudden psychological stimulus. The type and extent of defence mechanism used³ might indicate the mental health and interpersonal functioning.³

The defensive functioning of individuals tends to improve over time in a particular manner and phase. But based on the situation and the level affected, these mechanisms can be either maladaptive or adaptive. The defence mechanisms are broadly classified as mature, neurotic and immature.⁴ Defence mechanisms are ordered in a hierarchy based on their level of adaptiveness.⁵ As per Vaillant's proposed Hierarchy of these defence mechanisms mature ones are related to better adaptive functioning and mental health than the immature ones.³ The neurotic defence mechanisms are correlated with high levels of distress and impairment but have also shown to have apposite role in cognitive and affective awareness of conflicts.⁶ The relation of these defence mechanisms in various levels of hierarchy with the problems of mental health are being explored. The defence mechanisms lower in the order have been found to be associated with depression.⁵ Studies have shown improvement in defensive functioning with treatment or improvement of mental disorders.^{7,8} Specifically, among depressive patients the defence mechanisms are being studied with respect to their role in predicting depressive outcomes and their transition during phases of depression.⁹ The defence mechanisms vary among depressive and non-depressive patients. The eight immature defence mechanisms including passive-aggressive, acting out, help-rejecting complaining, projective identification, splitting of self-images, splitting of others' images, projection, and devaluation are empirically associated with depression. The immature defence mechanisms that manifest more in a non-depressive patient includes autistic fantasy, rationalization, denial, idealization, and omnipotence.¹⁰ Those using adaptive coping tend to have more mature defence mechanism.¹¹ Coping with stress and frequent use of immature and neurotic defence mechanism is seen commonly among those who use substance.^{12,13,14} Evidence is also suggestive that these coping or defence mechanisms are also influenced by the interventions for substance use.¹⁵

Hence, the current study aims to determine the relation between defence mechanisms and substance use in patients with Depressive disorders. Against this background, the objective of the present study is to compare defence mechanisms in patients of depressive disorders with and without substance use.

Materials and Methods

Study design and sample: This is a cross sectional study was conducted in the department of Psychiatry of a tertiary care teaching hospital in Chennai, Tamil Nadu. The sample size was calculated using the $n = z^2 p(q)/e^2$, formula for prevalence studies. Considering a prevalence of 68%, and allowable error of 10%, the sample size was estimated to be 84.

Subjects: Patients diagnosed with depression as per ICD-11 criteria were studied in two groups as those with substance use disorder and those without. We enrolled patients between 18-59 years of age, fulfilling ICD-11 criteria for depression single or and recurrent episode, and currently symptomatic or in remission. Patients with Substance use disorder as per ICD-11 criteria were considered as the substance use group. However, we excluded patients with mental retardation, and patients with significant medical or neurological illness.

Instruments: Self-reported substance use was recorded. Mini International neuropsychiatric interview (MINI), a brief structured diagnostic interview for Psychiatric disorders was done to rule out other psychiatric illness before enrolment into the study. A semi structured questionnaire was used to capture data on socio-demography and substance use. Hamilton Rating Scale of Depression (HAM-D) was used, which is most commonly used rating scale to assess the severity of depression contains 17-24 items, with first 17 items included in the scoring. Total score ranges from 0-50. And a shortened version of Defence Style Questionnaire (DSQ) was used to assess the defence mechanism, a psychometrically acceptable instrument in which the heterogeneity of defense measured in the original DSQ was preserved in factor scores, while aiming for internal consistency at the level of the individual defences. There are two items for each of 20 defences. Items are rated on a 9-point Likert-style scale Data was analysed using SPSS software version 20. The sociodemographic data, severity of depression and defence mechanisms was compared between both the groups.

Ethical Clearance: Ethical clearance was obtained from institutional ethical committee and written informed consent was obtained from each participant.

Statistical analysis: Shapiro wilk test was done to find if the data was normally distributed. Quantitative data including current age, age of onset of the disease, duration of the current episode, number of previous episodes, Ham D score and DSQ scores were all not normally distributed. Hence, Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare these values between both the groups.

Results

The study was conducted on a sample of 84 people with depression. The median (IQR) age of onset of the disease was 37 (32-44.7) years. The median duration of current episode was 4 (2-12) months. Though not statistically significant, the age of the participants and age of onset of the disease was slightly higher among substance users. The duration of current episode of illness was statistically comparable. The severity of depression based on Ham D score was significantly higher among those who used any substance (12 vs 18). (Table 1) There was no relation between severity grade of depression and gender, education, occupation, residence, type of family, marital status or socio-economic class. Overall, more than half had mild depression and one third had moderate depression. (Table 2) Majority, 67.8% did not have any previous episodes of depression. The overall depression score was 15 (11-18).

The depression scores as per Ham D scale was significantly higher among those who used substance (18) than those who were not using (12). Overall, females had a higher Ham D score (17) than males (13). The defence mechanism among patients with depression was statistically comparable across various socioeconomic groups. (Table 3)

Among those with depression, majority of males (36) were using substance and none of the females reported substance use. The proportion of substance use was higher among those who had studied only up to school or lower, among labourers and people in lower socio-economic class than their counterparts. (Table 4)

One or more defence mechanism was found in each person. The defence mechanisms used by depressive patients with and without substance use was compared using independent "t" test. (Table 5). It was found that projection (7.0), rationalization (6.7) and regression (6.4) (immature style defence mechanisms) scores were significantly higher among depressive patients with substance use ($p < 0.05$). On the other hand, idealization (6.4), reaction formation (6.8) (neurotic style defence mechanisms), devaluation (6.3) and denial (6.9) (immature style defence mechanisms) scores were significantly higher among depressive patients without substance use ($p < 0.05$). The other defence mechanisms captured in the present study did not vary significantly between depressive patients with and without substance use ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

In the current study all the patients were diagnosed with depressive disorders and defence mechanism among them were assessed. The study by Soham De, et al.,¹⁶ on people with alcohol use showed 60% had depressive disorders with more than one fifth being very severely depressed. In the current study the mature, immature and neurotic factor scores for defence mechanisms did not differ with substance use. But in contrast the study by Soham De, et al.,¹⁶ showed that neurotic and mature factor scores differed with severity of alcohol use in specific. The current study did not record the level of substance use, the median scores for immature defence mechanism was higher among substance users. In accordance with the current findings on the relation of substance use and defence mechanism, the study by Wadhawan A, et al.,¹⁷ also showed a positive correlation between level of substance abuse and negative affectivity personality dysfunction and turning against object cluster in defence mechanism.

In the current study mature (21.5) type of defence had the least score among substance users. Though the mean score of neurotic defence mechanism in the study by Abd Halim MH, et al.,¹⁸ was lower than the current study at 12.46, it was the most commonly manifested type of defence in substance users. Neurotic type was proposed to be the most common defence used by adults in the reports of Cramer et al.¹⁹ also. Immature factor had the highest median scores among substance users at 58.4. But in the study by Abd Halim MH, et al.,¹⁸ the mean score of immature factor was relatively low at 9.49 though the same DSQ tool was used. The difference might be because of the varying study population. Relatively very less exploration has been done on the varying manifestations of immature defense mechanisms to predict depressive disorders and their consequences. The study by Abd Halim MH, et al.,¹⁸ was done on participants who were on treatment for drug use indicating they might be on the high use side whereas the current study was done on patients with depression including varying degree of substance users. Also, the median age of participants with substance use was 40 years but in the study by Abd Halim MH, et al.,¹⁸ majority of participants were less than 40 years of age.

The findings indicate that depressive patients who use substances tend to exhibit higher scores in projection (7.0), rationalization (6.7), and regression (6.4) defense mechanisms. These results are consistent with the idea that substance use may serve as a coping mechanism for individuals with depressive disorders. For instance, projection and rationalization can be seen as ways to avoid facing one's own emotional issues and instead attribute them to external factors, while regression may manifest as regressing to substance use as a way to

escape emotional distress. Previous research has linked these defense mechanisms to maladaptive coping strategies in individuals with depression. For instance, a study by de Roten (2021) highlighted the role of maladaptive defences in depression.¹⁹

On the other hand, depressive patients without substance use were found to exhibit higher scores in reaction formation (6.8), idealization (6.4), devaluation (6.3), and denial defense mechanisms. Idealization and reaction formation might serve as protective mechanisms to maintain a positive self-image and to deal with internal conflicts more adaptively. These findings align with existing research on the relationship between defense mechanisms and psychological well-being. Defense mechanisms like idealization and reaction formation have been associated with adaptive psychological functioning.²⁰ The study carries the limitation that substance use was self-reported, and no scales were used to assess the severity of substance.

Conclusion

The study concludes that different pattern of defense mechanisms were used in patients with depression with and without substance use, Projection followed by rationalisation were the most common defence mechanism among substance users with depression, whereas denial followed by reaction formation and idealization were the common defense mechanisms among depression without substance use group which would be useful in better understanding of patients and application in psychotherapy.

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Table 1: Distribution of age, onset and course of depression between substance users and non-users

Variables	Median (IQR)		p value*
	Substance use Present n=42	Substance use Absent n=42	
Age	40 (33-44)	37.5 (29.7 – 46.5)	0.51
Age of onset of illness	37.5 (30-42)	37 (27.8-41.8)	0.82
Duration of current episode (in months)	4 (2-5.5)	4.5 (2-13.5)	0.51
Number of previous episodes	0 (0-1)	0 (0-1)	0.64
Ham D Score	18 (15-20.3)	12 (10-15)	<0.01

*Mann-Whitney U test

Table 2: Distribution of severity of depression across various sociodemographic characters (N=84)

	Mild	Moderate	Severe	Total	p value*
Total	50(59.5)	28 (33.3)	6 (7.1)	84 (100)	
Gender					
Male	38 (65.5)	15 (25.9)	5 (8.6)	58 (69)	0.07
Female	12 (46.2)	13 (50)	1 (3.8)	26 (31)	
Educational qualification					
Education up to school	29 (65.9)	10 (22.7)	5 (11.4)	44 (52.4)	0.08
Beyond school	21 (52.5)	18 (45)	1 (2.5)	40 (47.6)	
Residence					
Rural	15 (57.6)	9 (34.6)	2 (7.7)	26 (31)	0.8
Urban	35 (60.3)	19 (32.8)	4 (6.9)	58 (69)	
Occupation					
Clerical and above	14 (60.9)	7 (30.4)	2 (8.7)	23 (27.4)	0.54

Labour (unskilled, semi-skilled and skilled)	27 (69.3)	10 (25.6)	2 (5.1)	39 (46.4)	
Unemployed	9 (40.9)	11 (50)	2 (9.1)	22 (26.2)	
Type of family					
Joint	4 (57.1)	3 (42.9)	0 (0)	7 (8.3)	0.69
Nuclear	46(59.7)	25 (32.5)	6 (7.8)	77 (91.7)	
Marital status					
Single	10 (47.6)	10 (47.6)	1 (4.8)	21 (25)	0.22
Married	40 (63.5)	18 (28.6)	5 (7.9)	63 (75)	
SES					
Lower middle and below	44 (63.7)	20 (29)	5 (7.2)	69 (82.1)	0.18
Upper middle and above	6(40)	8 (53.3)	1 (6.7)	15 (17.9)	
*Chi square test/Fisher Exact					

Table 3: Distribution of depression scores and defence mechanism across various sociodemographic profile (N=84)

	Ham D Score	Mature factor	Neurotic factor	Immature factor
Gender				
Male	13 (11-18)	23 (19-30)	16 (14-20)	28.5 (22-34)
Female	17 (20-20.3)	28 (21.8-32.5)	16 (15-18)	25.5 (22.8-32)
p value*	0.03	0.2	0.98	0.23
Educational qualification				
Education up to school	14 (11-19.5)	23 (21-30)	16 (15-19)	28 (22-34)
Beyond school	16 (11.3- 18)	24 (20.2-30)	16 (14.3-20)	26 (24-32)
p value*	0.39	0.42	0.96	0.51
Residence				
Rural	16 (14.3-19.3)	24 (21-32.5)	17 (15-20)	26 (20.8-34.3)
Urban	14 (11-18)	24 (19.8-30)	16 (14-20)	28 (24-33.3)
p value*	0.25	0.87	0.62	0.81
Occupation				
Clerical and above	16 (11-20)	22 (19-30)	16 (14-20)	32 (22-35)
Labour (Unskilled, Semi-skilled and Skilled)	14 (12-18)	24 (22-32)	15 (14-20)	26 (21-32)
Unemployed	17 (11-18)	23.5 (19.8-30)	17.5 (15-19.3)	26 (24-32)
p value*	0.17	0.72	0.34	0.39
Type of family				
Nuclear	15 (11-19)	24 (21-30)	16 (15-19.5)	28 (22.5-34)
Joint	16 (14-17)	22 (14-32)	17 (14-20)	26 (22-29)
p value*	0.84	0.74	0.74	0.43
Marital status				
Single	14 (11-18)	24 (22-30)	16 (14-20)	28 (24-33)
Married	17 (13.5-20.5)	21 (16.5-27)	16 (15-19)	26 (21.5-34.5)
p value*	0.17	0.09	0.89	1.00
SES				
Lower middle and below	14 (11-18)	24 (21-30)	16 (15-20)	25 (22-33.5)

Upper middle and above	17 (15-22)	23 (20-30)	18 (14-20)	31 (27-34)
p value*	0.15	0.88	0.61	0.09

*Mann Whitney U test

Table 4: Relation between substance use and socio demographic factors among patients with depression (N=84)

	Substance use Disorder Yes	Substance use Disorder No	Total	p value*
Total	36 (46.8)	41 (53.2)	77 (100)	
Gender				
Male	36 (70.6)	15 (29.4)	51 (66.2)	<0.001**
Female	0 (0)	26 (100)	26 (100)	
Educational qualification				
Education up to school	26 (63.4)	15 (36.6)	41 (53.2)	0.002
Beyond school	10 (27.8)	26 (72.2)	36 (46.8)	
Residence				
Rural	8 (32)	17 (68)	25 (32.5)	0.07
Urban	28 (53.8)	24 (46.2)	52 (100)	
Occupation				
Clerical and above	11 (52.4)	10 (47.6)	21 (27.3)	0.002
Labour (unskilled, semi-skilled and skilled)	22 (62.9)	13 (37.1)	35 (45.5)	
Unemployed	3 (14.3)	18 (85.7)	21 (27.3)	
Type of family				
Joint	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)	7 (9.1)	0.35
Nuclear	34 (48.5)	36 (51.4)	70 (90.9)	
Marital status				
Single	3 (14.3)	18 (85.7)	21 (27.3)	<0.001
Married	33 (58.9)	23 (41.1)	56 (72.7)	
SES				

Lower middle and below	35 (54.7)	29 (45.3)	64 (83.1)	0.002
Upper middle and above	1 (7.7)	12 (92.3)	13 (16.9)	
*Chi square test, ** Fischer exact test				

Table 5 : Comparison of defence mechanisms used between depressive patients with and without substance use

Defense mechanisms	Depression with substance use	Depression without substance use	P value
Sublimation	5.9 (1.2)	6.2 (0.9)	0.372
Humour	4.7 (1.1)	5.3 (1.9)	0.639
Anticipation	6.2 (0.9)	6.3 (1.5)	0.718
Suppression	4.8 (1.4)	5.2 (2.0)	0.853
Mature style	21.5 (3.6)	23.4 (2.9)	0.826
Undoing	6.3 (1.6)	6.1 (1.4)	0.628
Pseudo-altruism	6.2 (1.4)	6.5 (1.3)	0.115
Idealization	4.9 (0.6)	6.4 (1.2)	0.008*
Reaction formation	4.9 (1.7)	6.8 (1.5)	0.012*
Neurotic style	24.2 (4.3)	22.9 (5.8)	0.925
Projection	7.0 (0.9)	5.5 (0.7)	0.001*
Passive aggression	3.7 (1.9)	4.1 (2.0)	0.681
Acting out	5.2 (1.8)	4.8 (1.7)	0.529
Isolation	4.4 (1.7)	4.6 (1.4)	0.538
Devaluation	4.0 (1.9)	6.3 (1.4)	0.004*
Autistic fantasy	4.8 (2.1)	4.6 (1.7)	0.811
Denial	6.1 (0.4)	6.9 (0.3)	0.031*
Displacement	4.1 (1.9)	4.1 (0.7)	0.582
Dissociation	4.4 (1.5)	4.8 (2.0)	0.772
Splitting	5.6 (1.0)	5.1 (1.1)	0.883
Rationalization	6.7 (1.7)	4.8 (0.4)	0.032*
Somatization	5.2 (1.8)	5.1 (1.5)	0.566
Regression	6.4 (1.2)	4.4 (1.1)	0.027*
Immature style	58.4 (4.2)	57.0 (5.2)	0.328